

THERMO-CHEMICAL KINETICS OF CARBON FIBRE RECYCLING

Joseph P. Heil¹, Thomas A. Turner¹, and Stephen J. Pickering¹

¹University of Nottingham, Polymer Composites Research Group
Division of Materials Mechanics & Structures, Faculty of Engineering, Nottingham, NG7 2RD, UK
Email: emxjh@nottingham.ac.uk, web page: www.nottingham.ac.uk

Keywords: Recycling, Kinetics, finite difference,

ABSTRACT

A method for predicting the tensile strength and elastic modulus of recycled carbon fibres is presented. Firstly, a model using reaction kinetics and heat transfer to predict the rate of resin removal from a composite allows for the time, temperature and oxygen concentration profile that a fibre experiences during the recovery process to be determined. A piece of composite is modelled as a series of discrete 1D slices with thickness, dx , and an area, X_a . Conduction, convection, and heats of reaction are considered within and between each slice as shown in figure 1. A three stage model is proposed:

- Stage 1: Pyrolysis- char formation and loss of volatile matter
- Stage 2: Char Oxidation- the char formed during pyrolysis is removed by oxidation
- Stage 3: Fibre oxidation- mass loss and temperature of the fibres is determined. The fibres can also be removed from the recycling process during this stage. Conduction to neighbouring elements is allowed.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fibre composites have high specific mechanical properties making them an ideal engineering material from a design perspective. However, to date the ability to reuse or recycle carbon fibre composites has proven to be very limited. Recycling CFRP is a growing field to address end of life legislation as well as to offer end users of CFRP an opportunity for a return on their investment by selling the composite to be recycled or carrying out the recycling themselves and reusing the recovered fibre internally or offering them for sale. Recycling CFRP is an extremely complex process where considerations of process time, temperature & oxygen concentrations, material feedstock, and desired fibre quality must all be weighed against each other when designing and operating a recycling process.

Many types of recycling processes have been developed which can be broadly categorised as either: mechanical size reduction, thermal, thermal fluid, or sub/super-critical fluid. With the exception of mechanical size reduction all of these process create an environment which oxidises the composite to remove the resin while leaving the fibre unharmed. Pyrolysis remains the dominant process choice with three commercial scale plants in operation across the world. In pyrolysis the most important process conditions are time, temperature, and oxygen concentration. A number of attempts to optimize a recycling process have been published which have shown the importance of various process parameters and generally in what range of values they should be for recycling to work. What has not been developed thus far is a way to more generally predict how a composite behaves as it is being recycled and what impact that has on the strength stiffness, and cleanliness of the recovered fibre.

This paper describes a thermo-kinetic model developed to predict how a composite changes and behaves during a recycling process. The model allows for process as well as material form and composition variables to be changed. Combinations of factors can also be changed such as aspect ratio, resin type, fibre type, thickness, process temperature etc., to see how the recycling process behaves with each different set of parameters. For example a design of experiments can be set up to determine the optimal process time and temperature needed to recycle a composite with a given thickness, fibre, and resin. Optimality could then be based on cost of process operation, cleanliness of the fibre, and or fibre quality. All of this experimentation can be done with computer modelling as

opposed to doing this on a physical recycling process where experimentation is more expensive and time consuming compared to modelling. The utility of the model is that a recycler can determine what materials are best to recycle and also to predict fibre quality for a given set of process conditions.

The process of recycling a fibre reinforced plastic (FRP) is broken down into three thermo-chemical reactions: pyrolysis, char oxidation, and fibre oxidation. Further details explaining how the model works during each reaction phase can be found in section 3. The framework of the model has been designed so that it may be applied to any pyrolysis type recycling method and also any composite system. To achieve this flexibility an extensive thermal-kinetic characterisation of the resin, fibre, and composite must be conducted. The sensitivity of the model to the accuracy of this characterisation is discussed in sections 4 and 5. A 1D model was justified on the basis that the in plane directions are expected to behave nearly identically and based on previous experience with composite recycling where the thickness of the composite significantly altered the behaviour of the recycling process and fibre quality. The model can be used to predict how long it will take for the matrix of a composite to be removed, leaving usable carbon fibres. For a static process where fibres are not removed from the process as they become freed from the resin matrix the model can be used to optimize process time so that as many clean fibres are produced with an acceptable level of thermal-oxidative damage.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

Friedman's method [1] was used to calculate the kinetic terms needed for the model which are: the pre-exponential factor, A , activation energy, E_a , and reaction order, n . A TA Instruments SDT 600 simultaneous DSC/TGA was used to decompose cured MTM 44 epoxy resin while measuring mass loss and heat flow. Heating rates of 5, 10, 20, 30, and 50°C/min to a temperature of 750°C were used. The temperature was held isothermally at 750°C until the resin was completely oxidised. Dried silica powder was mixed in with the resin to help stabilise the mass, temperature, and heat flow measurements. Silica was run under the same conditions as the resin to check that the silica would be unreactive over the temperature range of interest. The heats of pyrolysis and char oxidation were measured by integrating the peaks in the heat flow data.

A method to double check the accuracy of the heat flow in the model involved making composite laminates with embedded thermocouples and then heating these laminates to 250°C and measuring the temperature at each of the three thermocouples over time. Laminates of 1mm and 3mm thickness were laid-up and cured using an autoclave following the manufacturer's recommended cure cycle. To test heat flow these laminates were inserted into a preheated furnace and the temperature across three points in the thickness of the composite was measured and logged using a Pico Technology TC-08 thermocouple data logger.

3 RESULTS

The model uses a one dimensional finite difference framework with a constant time step and is implemented in Microsoft Excel. A piece of composite of a given thickness is considered. The composite is then subdivided through its thickness into seven elements that are sufficiently thin to assume homogeneity within each element. Mirror symmetry about the centreline is assumed to reduce the computational effort. Mirror symmetry relies on having a recycling process where the environment surrounding the composite is uniformly hot so that heat always flows from the outside in. The use of symmetry assumes mass always flows from the inside out which may not be the case if variations in the manufacturing process create alternate high diffusivity pathways. Boundary conditions are used at element one (boundary between composite and recycling atmosphere) and at element seven (at the symmetry line). Figure 1 shows these boundary conditions as well as heat and mass flow between each element. Additionally, the temperature, mass, composition, and extent of reaction of each element are tracked as a function of time. Tracking each element individually provides increased insight into the recycling process such as effects of heat transfer at the boundary and having fibres' thermal history as a function of thickness into the composite.

Figure 1: Model schematic showing directions of heat and mass flow as well as sources of heat.

The Transient Heat Conduction Equation (Equation 1) drives the model. This equation is used to determine the change in temperature of an element in the model. This temperature change drives the pyrolysis, char oxidation, and fibre oxidation reactions that generate or consume heat, and evolve volatile mass. The term on the left hand side (LHS) of the Transient Heat Conduction Equation relates to the temperature of an element. The first term on the right hand side (RHS) is conduction, the second is convection, and the third is heat generated or consumed by the reaction. On the LHS: m is the mass of the element, c_p is the heat capacity of the element, and dT/dt is the change in temperature of the element with respect to time. In the conduction term dk/dx is the heat transfer from one element to another and dT/dx is the temperature difference between elements. In the convection term \dot{m}_g is mass flux, $c_{p,g}$ is the heat capacity of the volatiles, and dT/dx is the temperature difference between elements. In the heat of reaction term m_o is the initial mass available for the current reaction, da/dt , is the change in extent of reaction over the last time step for the current reaction, and H_{rxn} is the enthalpy of reaction. The convention for exothermic reaction to have a negative enthalpy is maintained.

$$m c_p \frac{dT}{dt} = \frac{dk}{dx} \frac{dT}{dx} - \dot{m}_g c_{p,g} \frac{dT}{dx} - m_o \frac{d\alpha}{dt} H_{Rxn} \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{d\alpha_x}{dt} = A e^{-E_a/RT} (1 - \alpha)^n \text{ and } 1 - \alpha = m/m_o \quad (2)$$

Three sets of inputs must be provided to the model; one for each set of thermal, kinetic, and physical parameters. Within the thermal category: heats of reaction, heat capacity, and thermal conductivity are considered. All of the kinetic parameters relate to α , the extent of reaction. α is defined by Equation 2. In the Kinetic Equation, Equation 2, A is the pre-exponential factor, E_a is the activation energy, n is the reaction order, m is the current mass of the element, and m_o is the original mass of the element. However, there is an α for each reaction: pyrolysis, char oxidation, and fibre oxidation as well as for the overall recycling process. TGA curves are analysed to determine the α range for which each reaction is valid. Friedman's method is used to derive the pre-exponential,

activation energy, and reaction order for each reaction. Physical parameters, such as weight fractions, thickness, and density are used to define the construction of the composite.

3.1 Heat Flow

Thermal parameters are used to describe the recycling atmosphere, the thermal conductivity & heat capacity of the virgin composite and its constituent components. The parameterisation for the composite is broken down to the constituent level so that as the composition of the composite changes during the recycling process the thermal behaviour can be recalculated accordingly. The thermal conductivity of resin and char were taken from references listed in Table 1. The thermal conductivity of the composite was estimated to be 1W/m-K but in the future a more exact value will be calculated from heat transfer theory using thermal conductivities of the fibre and resin, volume fraction of fibre and voids, and other reinforcement geometry constants specified by whichever theory of heat transfer is used. Heat transfer at the boundary between the composite and the recycling environment is calculated assuming natural convection.

Thermal Conductivity	Value (W/m-K)	Parameter	Value
Fibre (k_f)	2	Fibre bundle efficiency	25%
Resin, (k_r)	0.169	Heat Transfer Coefficient (Htrans)	W/m ² -K
Char, (k_{ch})	0.955 [2]	Natural Convection	1-5
Composite, (k_c)	1	Fluidised Bed	100

Table 1: Conduction Parameters.

$$c_{p,g} = (24.99735 + 55.18696 * T - 33.69137 * T^2 + 7.948387 * T^3 - 0.136638 / T^2) \quad [3] \quad (3)$$

Mass flux of volatiles is responsible for convective heat transfer away from the composite. Values for mass flux and heat capacity of volatiles are needed to determine the convective heat transfer. Mass flux is dependent on the reaction rate and will be discussed later. Equation 5 in section 3.2 shows the calculation of convective heat transfer. To simplify the model, the heat capacity of CO₂, as a function of temperature, was used for the heat capacity of volatiles term in the model. Equation 3 gives this function in the units of J/mol-K.

Three heats of reaction are considered: pyrolysis, char oxidation, and fibre oxidation. Simultaneous TGA and DSC measurements were used to measure the heats of pyrolysis and char oxidation. The energy evolved for the oxidation of carbon, 30 J/Kg, is used as the heat of reaction for fibre oxidation.

On the LHS of the transient heat conduction equation c_p is the heat capacity of the composite. The heat capacity of the composite is determined by the rule of mixtures using the weight fractions of virgin composite, char, and carbon fibre. Table 2 lists the heat capacities used to calculate the overall heat capacity of the composite.

Material	Heat Capacity (J/g-K)
Carbon Fibre	2
Char	0.987 [2]
Virgin Composite	0.12949 [4]

Table 2: Heat capacity of constituent components of composite.

3.2 Solution Procedure

Referring back to the Transient Heat Conduction Equation, Equation 1, the parameter to be solved for is the change in temperature of that element. The change in temperature is the sum of all the heat contribution methods (conduction, convection, and heat of reaction) divided by the product of the mass and heat capacity of the composite element. Conduction at a boundary layer is calculated using

Equation 4A. Equation 4B is used to describe heat conduction of inner elements. In Equation 4A X_a is the cross-sectional area of the element, H_{trans} is the heat transfer coefficient, T_{inf} is the temperature of the recycling process, T_{bdry} is the temperature of the element exposed to the recycling atmosphere and dt . In Equation 4B K_c is the thermal conductivity of the composite element, T_{hot} is the temperature of a more outer element, T_{cold} is the temperature of a more inner element, and dX is the thickness of the element. Convective heat flow is calculated using Equation 5 which requires knowing the mass flux through the element (Equation 6), however the mass flux is dependent on extent of reaction. Extent of reaction calculations are discussed in the following section. Heat of reaction is measured using DSC as described previously. The energy contribution from the heat of reaction is shown in Equation 7 where $d\alpha_{rxn}$ is the change in extent of reaction for that time step. The heat capacity of each element is the summation of the mass fraction times the heat capacity for its constituent elements: fibre, char, and virgin composite. Since the model tracks changes in composition of the composite based on the reactions taking place determination of mass fraction is a simple continuation of the calculation. Once the change in temperature of each element at a given time step is determined the temperature for each element of the composite in the next time step is updated and the process continues until the overall extent of reaction is 0.99.

$$\text{Conduction} = X_a H_{trans} (T_{inf} - T_{bdry}) dt \quad \text{at the outermost element} \quad (4a)$$

$$\text{Conduction} = K_c (T_{hot} - T_{cold}) X_a / dX dt \quad \text{at inner elements} \quad (4b)$$

$$\text{Convection} = T_n \dot{m}_{g,n} C p_g dt X_a \quad (5)$$

$$\dot{m}_{g,n} = m_o \alpha_n / X_a + \dot{m}_{g,n+1} \quad (6)$$

$$Q_{rxn} = m_o d\alpha_{rxn} H_{rxn} \quad (7)$$

3.3 Extent of Reaction

Simultaneous TGA/DSC curves were analysed to determine over what range of reaction each sub-reaction (pyrolysis, char oxidation, and fibre oxidation) are valid. The range each reaction is valid for is unique to each composite system. Figure 2 gives an example of this analysis. First, tangent lines are drawn on each side of the inflection point in the weight (%) curve. Then the intersection of these tangent lines is taken as the changeover from one reaction to another. For the case shown in Figure 2 the changeover from pyrolysis to char oxidation is 79.27 wt% corresponding to an α of 0.2073 (1-0.7927). To make the inflection point in the weight (%) curve easier to identify the exothermic peak in the heat flow curve can be used as a guide to find the transition range in the weight (%) curve.

As discussed earlier there is an extent of reaction for both the overall recycling process and for each of the three thermo-chemical reactions. Within each reaction the change in extent of reaction is presented in Equation 2. The overall extent of reaction progresses by the change in the extent of reaction for the reaction that is active as shown by Equation 8. Tracking the progression of each thermo-chemical reaction is determined using the proportion of reaction progress past its starting point compared to extent of reaction range it is active for. Equation 9 shows this in more detail. The extent of reaction for each thermo-chemical reaction is also used to determine the compositional changes that occur during recycling. During pyrolysis virgin composite is converted into char containing fibre, and volatiles. The model assumes all the resin in the composite will be converted into char and volatiles. The mass of char and mass of fibre in char is proportional to the extent of reaction for pyrolysis. During char oxidation, as char is converted into volatiles, the composition of the composite changes to char with fibres in it and free fibres. During fibre oxidation the mass of fibres is reduced as fibres oxidize into volatiles.

Figure 2: DSC-TGA curves with analysis points.

Reaction	α Range	Pre Exponential Factor (1/s)	Activation Energy (J/mol-K)	Reaction Order (-)	Heat of Reaction (J/g)
Pyrolysis	0-0.2073	2.52×10^{17}	271,002	2.9735	2,022
Char Oxidation	0.2073-0.3302	3.03×10^5	120,576	1.0158	6,318
Fibre Oxidation	0.3302-1.0	1.80×10^3	140,000	0.0068	30,000

Table 3: Reaction Constants.

$$\alpha_t = \alpha_{t-1} + d\alpha_{rxn,t-1} \quad (8)$$

$$\alpha_{pyr,t} = \alpha_t / \alpha_{char\ ox\ crossover}$$

$$\alpha_{charOx,t} = \frac{\alpha_t - \alpha_{char\ ox\ crossover}}{\alpha_{fibre\ ox\ crossover} - \alpha_{char\ ox\ crossover}} \quad (9)$$

$$\alpha_{FibreOx,t} = \frac{\alpha_t - \alpha_{fibre\ ox\ crossover}}{1 - \alpha_{fibre\ ox\ crossover}}$$

4 VALIDATION

A core principal of the model is to use multiple TGA experiments to derive a set of kinetic parameters for pyrolysis and oxidation reactions. One test of how well this process works is to use the derived kinetic parameters to reproduce the TGA mass loss curve. Figure 3 shows mass loss curves reproduced from four different TGA curves and from the derived kinetic parameters. To produce a mass loss curve from the derived kinetic parameters the Kinetic Equation is used with an assumed temperature profile. This is not the same as using the thermo-kinetic model. The mass loss curves in Figure 3 are based on a 50°C /minute ramp to 750°C followed by an isothermal hold in air of MTM 44 epoxy resin. The agreement between the derived results and the measured results during the pyrolysis stage is poor but close during the char oxidation stage. To improve the agreement during the pyrolysis stage it may be more accurately modelled as two reactions to take into account breaking down low

molecular weight polymer chains at low temperature and then a higher temperature reaction for the actual char formation reaction. The transition from pyrolysis to oxidation in the derived data is at a fairly similar mass and time point as the TGA results. The agreement during char oxidation promotes confidence in the derivation methodology. The discrepancy between the TGA results and the derived kinetics will require further investigation.

Figure 3: Comparison of derived kinetics and TGA mass loss of MTM 44 resin using a 50°C/min ramp to 750°C.

Figure 4: Comparison of actual and derived mass loss curves for MTM 44.

Figure 4 shows derived and actual mass loss curves of MTM 44 at a variety of heating rates to determine if adjusting the heating rate of a derived curve will cause it to fit TGA data better than that shown in Figure 3. Figure 4 reveals this is not the case, and additionally shows that at high heating rates agreement between the derived curve and the actual TGA curve are good whereas for heating rates below 40°C/min the agreement deteriorates with decreasing heating rate. A mass loss curve generated using the thermo-kinetic model is also plotted in Figure 4. During the first ten minutes of recycling the thermo-kinetic model predicts a heating rate of about 40°C/min. During this first ten minutes it matches up better with the derived 40°C/min curve than the 50°C/min curve as opposed to during the char oxidation phase when the thermo-kinetic model matches well with both the actual derived TGA curves for a heating rate of 50°C/min. One possible explanation for better agreement of the model with the 50°C/min TGA curve during char oxidation is the char oxidation reaction is so exothermic it increases the heating rate beyond 40°C/min. The shape of the mass loss curve is only

slightly influenced by heating rate. It is unclear why the curve shape of the thermal-kinetic model differs from TGA results. The thermo-kinetic model lags the TGA curve up until about 60% weight loss, well into the char oxidation phase. To make up this lag during pyrolysis a larger pre-exponential constant, lower activation energy, or higher heat transfer coefficient could be used.

Composite laminates made of a Toray prepreg using T800S carbon fibre and a toughened epoxy resin (conforming to BMS8-276) were prepared at 1mm and 3mm thicknesses for purposes of testing heat flow to and through the laminate. The laminates were 100mm wide by 150mm long and contained embedded thermocouples positioned through the thickness of the laminate but spread out over the length and width to minimise distortion to the laminate. The laminates were placed in an air circulating oven. The oven's temperature set point was then increased to 250°C and the temperatures of the laminate and the oven were logged over time. A noticeable temperature lag in the centre of the laminate compared to the outer layers was not evident which is consistent with the thermo-kinetic model. However more optimal positioning of the laminate in the oven and of the thermocouple measuring the air temperature of the oven would be beneficial. To determine the heat transfer coefficient, H_{trans} , the lumped heat capacity heat transfer case was used [5]. In this method the temperature difference between a solid material and its surroundings is expected to follow an exponential decay relationship as indicated by Equation 11 [6]. In Equation 11, T_o is the starting temperature of the composite, T_{inf} is the temperature of the surrounding (in this case the oven temperature), A is the surface area over which heat transfer is taking place, and t is time in seconds. Figure 5 shows the measured composite laminate temperature along with overlays of Equation 11 using different heat transfer coefficients. An estimate of the heat transfer coefficient is made by finding the curve that most closely matches the measured composite surface temperature. Based on Figure 5 the correct value for the heat transfer coefficient is about 1.5W/m²-K. Increasing the heat transfer coefficient once it is at least 5W/m²-K does not change the temperature profile. Between 1.5W/m²-K and 5W/m²-K some small differences are reflected in the temperature profile by changing H_{trans} . For small heat transfer coefficients less than 1.5W/m²-K small changes to H_{trans} make significant differences to the temperature profile. As demonstrated by Figure 8 the thermo-kinetic model also shows extreme sensitivity to the heat transfer coefficient although in the range of $H_{trans} \leq 1$.

$$T = (T_o - T_{inf}) e^{-\left(\frac{H_{trans} A}{\rho C_p V}\right)t} + T_{inf} \quad (11)$$

Figure 5: Matching temperature profile by changing heat transfer coefficient.

5 SENSITIVITY

One potential concern about the model is the extent to which the value of the parameters in the kinetic equation matter. In Figure 6 mass loss curves, generated using only the kinetic equation, of three epoxy resins are compared. Mass loss curves for MTM 44 and MTM 28 are the most similar which matches with the tabulated parameters being closer between MTM 44 and MTM 28 than between either MTM 44 or MTM 28 and MTM 57. Figure 6 may also suggest that all epoxy resins will have similar behaviour during char oxidation but the pyrolysis stage will be more specific to each resin. Since all three parameters are changing at once in this example by changing one parameter at a time the thermo-kinetic model was used to see how each parameter affects the shape of the mass loss curve. The magnitude of the changes are listed in Table 4 and are about the same level of change as the largest difference between two of the resins shown in Figure 6.

Figure 7 shows mass loss curves generated using the thermo-kinetic model by changing one parameter of the kinetic equation at a time. These changes are with respect to the base values of MTM 44 and only for the pyrolysis stage. The base curve uses the kinetic parameters for MTM 44 tabulated in Figure 6. Making the pre-exponential factor, A , smaller extends the time spent in the pyrolysis reaction. The 'smallest A ' curve was run for 82,000 time steps which was enough to gain an understanding of how the pre-exponential factor, A , affects the curve shape. For the 'reduced A ' curve, A was large enough that that recycling reaction was able to run much quicker in comparison to the 'smallest A ' curve. The char oxidation stage happens over a small amount of time in comparison to the base curve and this can be justified by the composite being much hotter by the time it reaches the char oxidation stage. A similar argument can be applied to the 'reduced E_a ' and 'smallest E_a ' curves. The decrease in activation energy for pyrolysis means the reaction progresses faster and further even under low temperatures compared to the base curve. Once the composite moves to the char oxidation stage the temperatures are still comparatively low, so mass loss due to char oxidation progresses slowly until the composite is hot enough. The 'reduced E_a ' and 'smallest E_a ' curves are nearly identical during the majority of the char oxidation phase as would be expected since the kinetic parameters for the char oxidation phase are the same between the two curves. Noticeable mass loss resumes once the temperature has reached a critical level to overcome the activation energy for char oxidation. For these two curves the time it takes for char oxidation to occur is longer than in the base curves even though pyrolysis happens much sooner. This may be attributable to the energy contribution from pyrolysis coming when the composite is relatively cool, depriving the composite of that extra boost of energy needed to kick off the char oxidation reaction once the composite is hotter. Making the reaction order, n , one third the original size has nearly no effect on the mass loss curve.

Figure 6: Projected mass loss curves for 3 different epoxy resins.

Figure 7: Effect of varying kinetic equation parameters.

Curve	Reduced A	Smallest A	Reduced Ea	Smallest Ea	Small n
Change	base $\times 10^{-3}$	base $\times 10^{-5}$	base/1.5	base /2	base /3

Table 4. Degree of change in kinetic parameters used to generate Figure 7

Large changes to the pre-exponential factor, A, results in the large changes in reaction time. Changing the activation energy by 50% results in a similar change to reaction times as does changing A by several orders of magnitude. However since A is so large a five orders of magnitude change is an insignificant percentage of its overall value meaning the reaction kinetics are quite sensitive to A. A

slight difference in the determination of E_a from the true E_a will have much larger consequences than a slight difference in the determination of A .

Figure 8 shows mass loss curves for MTM 44 produced from the model but using different values for the heat transfer coefficient. Actual TGA results using a 50°C/min heating are also plotted for reference. Immediately noticeable is that the model shows less distinct pyrolysis and oxidation stages compared to TGA results. For natural convection the heat transfer coefficient would be expected to be around 1W/m²-K. In the full thermo-kinetic model a heat transfer coefficient of 0.6W/m²-K is used so that the recycling time in the model is about the same as with TGA at 50°C/min. As shown below, changing the value of the heat transfer coefficient by a minimal amount results in a significant change to the recycling time.

Figure 9 shows the effect of thickness on the recycling process. As expected thicker materials take longer to recycle. Additionally, the increase in thickness is linearly proportional to the increase in time.

Figure 8: Effect of changing heat transfer coefficient.

Figure 9: Effect of thickness on mass loss and temperature.

9 CONCLUSIONS

A three stage thermo-kinetic model for carbon fibre composite recycling is proposed and its workings analysed. The three stages are pyrolysis, char oxidation, and fibre oxidation where each stage is assumed to correspond to one reaction and has thermal and kinetic parameters derived from simultaneous DSC-TGA measurements. The practice of using Friedman's method to derive the necessary kinetic parameters is shown to be reliable however multiple reactions may need to be fit within each stage for the model to accurately reproduce the mass loss curve measured by TGA. At higher heating rates ($40^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}^+$) the agreement between the original TGA curve and the mass loss curve reproduced by using just the kinetic equation is stronger than at lower heating rates, and therefore perhaps Friedman's method should only be applied to data using these high heating rates in order to derive the most accurate kinetic parameters.

The thermo-kinetic model is very flexible as each part of it can be adjusted individually allowing the model to be easily applied to different composite system or easily improved with the addition of more accurate determination of its physical and kinetic parameters. Changing the kinetic parameters is the most computationally taxing. Of the kinetic parameters large changes to A and moderate changes to E_a result in the largest changes to the mass loss curve. Furthermore changing E_a is the most tricky as the computation can easily spiral out of control around transitions between stages if the timestep is too large while the rest of the time a small timestep slows the operation of the model. The model is extremely sensitive to the heat transfer coefficient, H_{trans} .

The experimentally measured H_{trans} is between $1.25\text{W}/\text{m}\cdot\text{k}$ and $1.5\text{W}/\text{m}\cdot\text{k}$, however these values when used in the thermo-kinetic model resulted in recycling times that were much shorter than experimentally observed. To counterbalance the higher value of H_{trans} , then the kinetics for char oxidation might be wrong, the heat capacity could be too low, the thermal conductivity could be too high, or the heat of reaction could be too high. It is unlikely the kinetics for char oxidation are wrong since the agreement between the kinetic equation and the TGA are best during char oxidation. Further analysis, not shown, shows changes on the order of 60-75% to thermal conductivity and heat of reaction hardly alter the recycling behaviour of the composite. Increasing the char heat capacity by 50%-100% delayed char oxidation time by 0.7-1minutes and increased char oxidation time by 0.2-1 minutes. Increasing composite C_p by 10%, 25%, and 50% delayed char oxidation time by about 9%, 22%, and 47%. Based on these results the heat capacity of the composite and char need to be carefully and accurately measured to ensure a representative recycling time.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors gratefully acknowledge the support of the Boeing Company under the Boeing / University of Nottingham strategic collaboration in carbon fibre recycling.

REFERENCES

- [1] Friedman HL. Kinetics of thermal degradation of char-forming plastics from thermogravimetry. Application to a phenolic plastic. *Journal of Polymer Science Part C: Polymer Symposia* 1964;6(1):183-195.
- [2] Henderson JB, Wiebelt JA, Tant MR. A Model for the Thermal Response of Polymer Composite Materials with Experimental Verification. *Journal of Composite Materials* 1985;19(6):579-595.
- [3] Chase, M.W., Jr., *NIST-JANAF Thermochemical Tables, Fourth Edition*, J. Phys. Chem. Ref. Data, Monograph 9, 1998, 1-1951
- [4] HexTow IM7 Carbon Fiber Product Data. Stamford, Connecticut: Hexcel Corporation; 2010.
- [5] "The Convection Heat Transfer Coefficient on a Vertical Plate from Surface Temperature Measurements." Pico Technology. Web. 13 May 2015.
- [6] Vollmer M. Newton's law of cooling revisited. *European Journal of Physics* 2009;30(5):1063.